

MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM IN THE TREATMENT OF SUPERFICIAL VENOUS SYSTEM DISORDERS – GREAT SAPHENOUS VEIN INCOMPETENCE: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Great Saphenous Vein Incompetence (GSVI) is a condition in which the functioning of the venous valves is altered, resulting in decreased ability to propel blood along the capillaries. This leads to impaired venous return (VR), causing blood stasis, increased venous hydrostatic pressure, and extravasation of fluid into the interstitial space, resulting in edema. Edema favors the development of an inflammatory process that acidifies the region by altering the potential hydrogen (pH). Its aggravation causes pain, heaviness, paresthesias and fatigue in the lower limbs. Less invasive techniques with fewer side effects have been sought for treatment. Thus, Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB), a therapy developed by Isaac Goiz Durán, consisting of the application of magnets in specific places of

the body, aiming to restore the pH, consequently restoring dysfunctions and flows and promoting body homeostasis, presents itself as one more possible treatment for circulatory disorders. **Objective:** The objective is to evaluate the contribution of MB as a form of treatment for cases of venous insufficiency.

Methodologie: This case study evaluated and compared the symptomatology and Color Doppler results performed in a 65-year-old female volunteer diagnosed with GSVI before and after MB application. **Results:** After the MB treatment, there was an improvement in the symptoms reported by the participant and the reports of the Color Doppler exams of the lower limbs showed a reversal of the great saphenous vein incompetence to competent GSV. **Conclusion:** MB can contribute to the treatment/prevention of circulatory disorders in the lower limbs.

Keywords: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Pair; Great Saphenous Vein Incompetence; Circulatory Disorders; Prevention; Static Magnetic Fields; pH dysfunction.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB), a technique developed in 1988 by physician and physiotherapist Isaac Goiz Durán, is based on the principles of magnetism, pH, biomagnetic resonance, entropy, symbiosis, fluid rheology and body homeostasis (BOSSA, C. *et al.*, 2023). It consists of the use and application of medium intensity magnets (between 1,000 and 7,500 Gauss), of opposite polarity, with the north pole, agreed as negative, identified by the black color and the south pole, agreed as positive, identified by the red color, to restore the electrolyte balance of the body (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; BROERINGMEYER and BROERINGMEYER, 1987; CALEGARI *et al.*, 2023).

When there is an imbalance between positive and negative electrical charges in the body, these charges polarize in certain regions (anatomical points) and remain in magnetic resonance with each other, forming what is called in MB as a “Biomagnetic Pair” (BMP). Such polarization results in a change in pH, which can lead to dysfunctions and pathologies (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA, C. *et al.*, 2023).

To identify a BMP, the MB diagnostic tool called Biomagnetic Scanning (BS) is used (FRANK, 2017). BMP are classified as: regular, dysfunctional, glandular dysfunctional, reservoir and special (DOS SANTOS *et al.*, 2023). Applying the north pole of the magnet to specific points of the organism with accumulation of negative charges, one can observe the shortening of the right hemibody (right leg), in the region where the pH is in dysfunction with excess alkalinity. Then, with the south pole, the magnetic resonance point is sought, with excess acidity, H⁺ ion accumulation, where the alignment of the lower limbs is observed (FRANK, 2017; GOIZ DURÁN, 2005; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023).

After finding the BMP, the treatment is performed by impacting magnets on these resonant points, aiming at depolarization and consequent neutralization of charges, rebalancing the bioelectromagnetic field (FRANK, 2017; GOIZ DURÁN, 2005; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023). This allows the return to the ideal pH of the region, providing conditions for the immune system to act on the antigens. This promotes interactions in the cells, tissues, organs that support them, corrects dysfunctions, flows, intoxications, psycho-emotional problems, promotes the homeostasis of the organism, known within MB as Normal Energy Level (NEL) (BROENINGMEYER and BROENINGMEYER, 1987; BROENINGMEYER, 1991; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008; BOSSA, C. *et al.*, 2023).

The onset of any disease is a sign that the body is out of balance, creating electrical patterns to ensure survival, these being the BMP. MB helps the body adjust its electrical pattern for maximum health, restoring body functions. “A healthy cell produces energy, while a sick or unhealthy cell withdraws energy from the body to give to the disease” (BROERINGMEYER and BROERINGMEYER, 1987; BROENINGMEYER, 1991).

According to Broeringmeyer (1987), in the initial stage of any disease, there is an increase in hydrogen and a decrease in oxygen, causing hyperactivity and making the diseased area more acidic. The opposite occurs when the organ is hypoactive, becoming more alkaline. This change in the consumption or generation of oxygen by the body's cells allows the immune system to recognize that there is a disease process in progress. Therefore, it is necessary to find out if

it is a case of hypoactivity or hyperactivity of the affected organ/tissue to treat a disease and reverse such a condition, since the disease cannot exist in an oxygen-rich environment (BROERINGMEYER and BROERINGMEYER, 1987; BROENINGMEYER, 1991).

The same happens with the inflammatory process, which is a reaction of vascularized live tissue to a local aggression. Its main feature involves the release of chemical mediators, pro-inflammatory cytokines that trigger changes in the area. They promote microcirculation dilation, increased blood flow and vascular permeability, plasma leakage, edema, cellular diapedesis out of the vein, increased viscosity and subsequent decrease in blood flow, with the possibility of circulatory stagnation (BECHARA; SZABÓ, 2006).

The action of the MB on the inflammatory process occurs through the application of the north pole of the magnet. Among the actions it promotes in the body are the elimination of fluids, vessel contraction, increase of alkalinity, inhibition and control of pain, increase of oxygen in the tissues and the reduction of hydrogen ions, responsible for the acidification process. The application of this polarity decreases the excessive activity of organs when they are affected by disease, inflammation, trauma or by its surroundings. There is a reduction in acidity, “reducing the H⁺ and increasing the O₂ that causes an alkaline reaction to make the organ or tissue return to its normality” (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; DRUM *et al.*, 2023).

Hence, the MB can also act in the prevention of diseases, when the pH distortion of the organs or tissues of the human body is corrected even before the appearance of signs and symptoms that configure a pathology. One of the findings of Goiz Durán is based on changes in body flows, such as vascular changes. These can be influenced by BMP that support pathogenic microorganisms or tissue changes that can hinder venous return (GOIZ DURÁN, 2003).

The main superficial vein in the lower limbs is the Great Saphenous Vein (GSV), located in the subcutaneous tissue and extending under the medial face of the

lower limb to the inguinal region, draining into the femoral vein. GSV can be identified on Doppler ultrasound and usually has between 6 and 25 valves in its entire length (GLOVICZKI *et al.*, 2011; PANG, 1991; ABREU *et al.*, 2017).

The GSV may have its function altered, resulting in a clinical condition known as Great Saphenous Vein Incompetence (GSVI). GSVI presents with blood reflux or the lack of the ability to push blood along the capillaries, against the force of gravity, due to changes in the functioning of the valves. The incompetence of the Great Saphenous vein results in increased venous pressure in the lower limbs, leading to the appearance of varicose veins due to accumulated vascular reflux (ABREU *et al.*, 2017).

With aggravation of the condition, there is the initial appearance of pain, heaviness, fatigue and swelling. The evolution of this initial condition can develop the so-called Chronic Venous Insufficiency (CVI), which can lead to alterations in the skin and subcutaneous tissue due to chronic venous hypertension (CVH). This can evolve naturally with inflammation, eczema, lipodermatosclerosis and ulcers located in the lower limbs (CASTRO E SILVA *et al.*, 2005).

Chronic Venous Insufficiency (CVI) has a higher incidence in women with multiple pregnancies, during aging process and according to family history, in addition to being associated with increased risk in cases of obesity and trauma (LUCCAS *et al.*, 2002; ABREU *et al.*, 2017). Varicose veins, characterized by elongated and tortuous dilation of the veins with reflux and anatomical alteration, have a diameter greater than 3 mm and are related to venous hypertension, which manifests itself with distal superficial venous pressures in the lower limbs around 80 to 90 mmHg at rest, which can reach levels close to 70 mmHg during exercise in the presence of CVI (ABASV, 2015).

Minimally invasive techniques have been sought for treatment. However, the most used treatment is still surgical resection where, in addition to the use of anesthetics, saphenous nerve damage, paresthesia, ecchymosis, bruises, pain and delay in returning to work may occur (NESBITT *et al.*, 2011; ABREU *et al.*, 2017).

Considering that MB is a non-invasive, low-cost, painless, easy-to-apply complementary practice with minimal contraindications, which aims at both the treatment and prevention of various pathologies (GOIZ DURÁN, 2005), including Chronic Venous Insufficiency (CVI), MB is seen as a potential treatment alternative.

METHODOLOGIE

A descriptive cross-sectional study with a qualitative approach was conducted to investigate the therapeutic potential of Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) in the treatment of Great Saphenous Vein Incompetence (GSVI) in a 65-year-old woman. The inclusion criteria were: female gender, confirmed diagnosis of GSVI through Color Doppler exams of the Superficial and Deep Venous System of the lower limbs, exclusive treatment with MB and signature of the Free Prior Informed Consent (FPIC). Data were collected from the participant's medical records, including information about the clinical state, symptoms reported at the time of treatment, and the reports of the Color doppler exams performed before and after the application of the MB technique. The main data collected from the Color doppler examination reports included the assessment of patency, presence of reflux and competence of the deep and superficial venous system, in addition to signs of venous thrombosis.

CASE REPORT

The anamnesis was carried out on September 11, 2020, when the participant reported pain in the region of the dorsum of the foot and right calf, paresthesia in the direct hallux, feeling of heaviness, burning, edema and redness in the ankle region, fatigue in the entire extension of the right lower limb (RLL) for approximately 2 months. The report of the Color doppler of the Superficial Venous System of the RLL, dated September 4, 2020, accused: Great Saphenous Vein, visible in all its extension, previous and incompetent. She also reported pain in the region of the right coxofemoral joint. She was not using medication.

The Medicinal Biomagnetism technique was applied, as described by Goiz Durán (2008), according to the scanning protocol "Description of Biomagnetic Pairs:

Biomagnetism and Bioenergetics” (BOSSA, 2021a; CORRÊA *et al.*, 2023). The treatment was carried out from September 11, 2020 to November 5, 2020. After each MB appointment, the research participant received the application of the GSVI protocol (correction of alterations in the Lower Limbs Blood Flow) as shown in Figure 1, for 40 minutes.

In conjunction with the protocol in Figure 1, thrombosis-specific BMP were also impacted (Table 1) for 40 minutes.

Table 1: Biomagnetic Pairs Related to Thrombosis.

Biomagnetic Pair	Impaction Point North (-)	Impaction Point South (+)
BMP1	Umbilicus	Umbilicus
BMP2	Appendix	Peritoneum
BMP3	Coronary	Cardia

Note: BMP = Biomagnetic Pair. Source: Bossa (2017).

Figure 1: Lower Limb Blood Flow (LLBF) Treatment Protocol

Source: BOSSA 2021

Caption: The image represents a photograph of the magnets applied on anatomical regions, following the convention of Par Magnético Institute (IPM), where red is seen (south pole), the north pole is on the skin and, where black is seen (north pole), the south is in contact with the skin. Three south pole magnets applied on the kidneys and on the saphenofemoral junction of the affected leg and seven north pole magnets applied on the venous return path of the great saphenous vein. Source: Bossa (2021b), Calegari *et al.* (2023), Franco *et al.* (2023).

Scanning 1

In the first appointment, on September 11, 2020, screening was carried out, which resulted in the treatment of BMP for 20 minutes (Table 2). Chakra 4 alignment

was also carried out (BOSSA, 2021a).

Table 2: Biomagnetic Pairs Treated in the First Appointment.

Biomagnetic Pair	Impaction Point North (-)	Impaction Point South (+)
BMP1	Renal Capsule (L)	Kidney (L)
BMP2	Thymus	Rectum
BMP3	Index (R)	Index (L)
BMP4	Brachialis (R)	Brachialis (L)
BMP5	Pleura (L)	Liver
BMP6	inguinal Nerve (L)	Articulação (cotovelo)
BMP7	4th Cervical	Pylorus
BMP8	Palm (L)	Palm (R)
BMP9	Optic Chiasm (R)	Optic Chiasm (L)
BMP10	Nevus (R)	Kidney (R)
BMP11	Brachial Plexus (R)	Brachial Plexus (L)
BMP12	Coxofemoral joint (R)	Kidney (R)

Note: BMP = Biomagnetic Pair; R = Right; L = Left. Source: Bossa (2021a).

At the end of the treatment, the patient reported relief from pain and fatigue. The hallux was still showing mild paresthesia.

Scanning 2

In the second MB appointment, on September 17, 2020, the patient still reported mild hallux paresthesia. The scanning was then carried out, which resulted in the

treatment of the BMP described in Table 3, impacted for 20 minutes.

Table 3: Biomagnetic Pairs Treated in the Second Appointment.

Biomagnetic Pair	Impaction Point North (-)	Impaction Point South (+)
BMP1	Corpus Callosum (L)	Corpus Callosum (L)
BMP2	Supraspinatus (R)	Supraspinatus (L)
BMP3	Spermatic cord (R)	Spermatic cord (L)
BMP4	Inguinal nerve (L)	Kidney (L)
BMP5	Pleura (L)	Liver
BMP6	Esophageal hiatus	Bladder
BMP7	Esophagus (L)	Bladder
BMP8	Flank (L)	Flank (L)

Note: BMP = Biomagnetic Pair; R = Right; L = Left. Source: Bossa (2021a).

After this second appointment, the volunteer reported that she was feeling “very well” and that the paresthesia had remitted.

Scanning 3

In the third MB appointment, on September 24, 2020, the volunteer reported not feeling pain, tiredness or paresthesia. The scanning was then carried out, which resulted in the treatment of the BMP shown in Table 4, impacted for 20 minutes. After scanning, the Lymphatic Protocol was also impacted (Figure 2), for 40 minutes.

Table 4: Biomagnetic Pairs Treated in the Third Appointment.

Biomagnetic Pair	Impaction Point North (-)	Impaction Point South (+)
BMP1	Urethra (S)	Urethra (I)
BMP2	Vagina (R)	Vagina (L)
BMP3	Pes anserinus (L)	Pes anserinus (R)
BMP4	Pineal (H)	Pineal
BMP5	Hypophysis	Bladder
BMP6	Thymus	Adrenal (C)
BMP7	Pylorus	Tongue
BMP8	Contralateral to Cecum	Contralateral to Cecum
BMP9	Descending Colon	Liver
BMP10	Temporal (L)	Temporal (L)
BMP11	Pericardium	Pericardium
BMP12	Circle of Willis (R)	Kidney (R)
BMP13	Occipital (R)	Kidney (R)

Note: BMP = Biomagnetic Pair; R = Right; L = Left; C = center; S = Superior; I = inferior and H = horizontal. Source: Bossa (2021a).

Figure 2: Lymphatic Protocol

Caption: Application of the magnets follows the IPM convention. One south pole magnet applied over thymus, thirteen north pole magnets applied over lymph nodes. A pair of magnets over the BMP Chiasm/Chiasm. Source: Bossa (2021b), Calegari *et al.* (2023).

On October 1, 2020, the LLBF protocol (Figure 1) and points for thrombosis (Table 1) were applied for 40 minutes. It was equally applied in the appointment on October 8, 2020 after a Magnetic Emotional Unblocking/Liberation (in Portuguese “Desbloqueio Emocional Magnético” – DEM) treatment, as described in the study by Martini *et al.* (2023). On October 15, 22 and 29, 2020, only the LLBF (Figure 1) and BMP for thrombosis (Table 1) were applied for 40 minutes. On

November 5, 2020, the Basic Protocol was applied (Figure 3), for 45 minutes, as described by Martini *et al.* (2023).

After treatment with MB, on December 15, 2020, the patient repeated the Color doppler exam and the report showed a right Great Saphenous Vein of preserved caliber, with no signs of incompetence. The participant continued to report absence of signs and symptoms.

Figure 3: Basic Protocol

BASIC PROTOCOL

Magnet visualisation: If the image shows positive, negative is on skin. IPM convention
Source: BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. Medicinal Biomagnetism handout from course. Cascavel/PR - Brazil.
Independent edition. Volume 1, Ed 12, August 2021

Caption: The application of magnets follows the IPM convention. Source: Bossa (2021b).

DISCUSSION

The results of this study demonstrated the therapeutic potential of Medicinal Biomagnetism in a clinical case of Great Saphenous Vein Incompetence (GSVI). The volunteer showed remission of the symptoms and the diagnosis was

confirmed by comparing the reports of the Color Doppler scans, performed before and after the treatment.

It is known that in Chronic Venous Insufficiency (CVI) valve insufficiency can be generated by dilation resulting from varicose veins that generate dysfunction in the venous wall. There is blood reflux and venous stasis. As a consequence, hydrostatic pressure increases, allowing greater leakage of plasmatic fluid, proteins and ions, leading to the accumulation of fluid in the interstitial space (BECHARA; SZABÓ, 2006). The lymphatic system compensates, absorbing the liquid, however, if the condition continues to evolve, the venous hypertension worsens, the amount of liquid in the interstitium becomes greater than the capacity of its uptake by this system, culminating in edema, redness and heat. At some point not yet fully elucidated in this process, the inflammatory response is stimulated (DANIELSON *et al.*, 2003).

The action of inflammatory agents causes increased permeability of the capillaries in the affected area, which further increases the extravasation of liquid. Phagocytes end up increasing the production of cytoplasmic granules with free radicals increasing local inflammation (MANTHEY, 2000). The acidic extracellular pH, characterized by the increase of H⁺ ions, leads to a rapid increase in intracellular pH (RAJAMÄKI *et al.*, 2013; GOMES; BUFFOLO, 1993). The environment becomes deleterious for the cells, there is a decrease in microcirculation, reducing the arrival of O₂ and cell nutrition (Italian College of Phlebology, 2001; ABREU *et al.*, 2017).

The application of MB magnets, especially the south pole, interacts directly with H⁺ ions. When BMP is applied, there is depolarization of biochemical charges, normalizing the bioelectricity of the cell membrane. In this way, the balance of the previously dysfunctional pH is allowed as well as the return of the physiological activity of the cells, allowing the return to homeostasis that is the basis of the health of the organism (GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

The negative pole of a magnet applied to a point with excess negative charges in the body has the ability to push such charges, correcting the bioelectricity of

local cells. When applying a BMP, the charges pushed together by both polarities of the magnets collide in some anatomical region, generating water and neutralizing such charges (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

One of the possibilities for the results achieved in this treatment is the displacement of excess free radicals to the most proximal region of the limb, until reaching the inguinal lymphatic region, or even the reabsorption of liquid by the capillaries, after the reduction of the inflammatory process.

For the MB theory, a magnet applied with its north polarity has the ability to constrict venous vessels and push fluids. Such contraction, in addition to pushing the blood towards the right atrium, causes the blood flow to resume its course, increasing the delivery of oxygen to the tissues, resuming nutrition and cell function and, consequently, tissue. With this, tissue function is restored (GOIZ DURÁN, 2014). This process mimics the effect of physical activity on venous return in cases of circulatory changes where the contraction of the gastrocnemius musculature compresses the veins, boosting the blood, facilitating blood return (PENA; MACEDO, 2011; LEAL, 2016).

Painful stimuli are generated by excessive excitability of nerve endings (FEIN, 2012). For Goiz Durán (2008) and R. Broeringmeyer (1991), the north pole also has a sedative effect, inhibiting and controlling pain, in addition to being anti-inflammatory (GOIZ DURÁN, 2003). In all treatments applied to the volunteer, this magnet polarity was impacted throughout the GSV path, which could explain the results obtained (Figure 1). In this same protocol, it can be observed that the south polarity of the magnet was applied in the region of the lymph nodes of the right inguinal region. This application is supported by the literature that describes that this polarity has as one of its characteristics the stimulation of organs and tissues, activating their functioning, as well as accelerating metabolic processes and body flows (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; GOIZ DURÁN, 2014; GOIZ DURÁN, 2003). This fact may have potentiated the functioning of the lymphatic system which, together with the decrease in the leakage of plasmatic fluid from the vein in question, culminated in the reabsorption of the fluid that caused the edema, favoring the reduction of local inflammation and enabling valve function.

BM presupposes acting on the inflammatory causes and on the abnormality of reflux and/or obstruction, optimizing the general functioning of the venous return process (GOIZ DURÁN, 2005; GOIZ DURÁN, 2008).

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study point to a contribution of the MB in the treatment of venous circulatory disorders. It was observed that after the MB treatments, there was a reduction in the signs and symptoms reported by the participant and the post-treatment Color Doppler report showed that the great saphenous vein returned to its normal function.

MB proved to be a low cost and risk strategy, with minimal side effects, being important both for the prevention and treatment of Great Saphenous Vein Incompetence and venous disorders.

This study was the first to demonstrate the application of MB as an alternative treatment for GSVI, thus being able to serve as a basis for new and more detailed studies in this field.

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